

HYDROXYFLUOBERYLLATES. PART IV. COMPLEX HYDROXYFLUOBERYLLATES AND HYDROXYFLUOBERYLLATES OF SILVER, THALLIUM AND HYDRAZINE

BY GRIHAPATI MITRA

The hydroxyfluoberyllates of monovalent thallium, silver and hydrazine have been prepared and their properties studied. All these hydroxyfluoberyllates are excessively soluble in water. The silver and hydrazine salts are also soluble in 60% alcohol. A solution of silver hydroxyfluoberyllate, when boiled vigorously for a pretty long time, gives an insoluble black precipitate of silver oxide. Thallium hydroxyfluoberyllate is slightly deliquescent in nature. The solubilities of these compounds are greater than those of the corresponding sulphates or fluoberyllates.

The tetraamino complexes of Cu, Zn and Cd hydroxyfluoberyllates as well as the hexammino complex of nickel hydroxyfluoberyllate have been prepared. These compounds are stable only in an atmosphere of ammonia. Moist air decomposes them very quickly.

In extension of the investigation on the chemistry of the hydroxyfluoberyllates of different metals (Mitra, this *Journal* 1955, 32, 241, 246; 1956, 33, 45) the hydroxyfluoberyllates of monovalent thallium, silver and hydrazine were prepared and their chemical properties studied.

The hydroxyfluoberyllates of the amino complexes of metals like copper, zinc, cadmium and nickel, have been also prepared. In chemical composition these are analogous to the corresponding sulphates. The hydroxyfluoberyllates are, however, more soluble than the corresponding compounds of sulphate ion.

EXPERIMENTAL

A weighed amount of the substance was fused with sodium carbonate. The mass was subsequently extracted with hot water and filtered. The amount of fluoride ion present in the filtrate was determined as calcium fluoride. For the quantitative estimation of the other metals the standard methods were followed after removal of the fluoride ions by heating a weighed amount of the substance with H_2SO_4 .

Thallium Hydroxyfluoberyllate.—No trivalent metal hydroxyfluoberyllate has upto now been prepared. In general it has been found that the trivalent metal salts of any complex fluoride anion are very difficult to prepare. The reason is obvious; the trivalent metals themselves have a strong tendency for the formation of very stable complex fluoride anions. All attempts to isolate the hydroxyfluoberyllates of trivalent thallium ended in failure. The monovalent thallium hydroxyfluoberyllate, however, was prepared during the course of the present investigation. As expected, it behaved like silver hydroxyfluoberyllate.

A weighed quantity of thalious sulphate was treated with the requisite quantity of barium hydroxide solution. The precipitated barium sulphate was filtered off and

the solution was concentrated on a water-bath. A little excess than the theoretical amount of freshly precipitated beryllium hydroxide was then added to it and the mixture was digested and from time to time dilute hydrofluoric acid (20%) was carefully added. The addition of hydrofluoric acid was stopped when the solution remained just turbid due to the presence of traces of undissolved beryllium hydroxide. The solution after filtration was allowed to crystallise in a vacuum desiccator. Colorless crystals appeared after a few days. These were filtered, washed with 60% alcohol, dried and analysed. (Found: Tl, 82.68; F, 11.59. Tl_2BeF_3OH requires Tl, 83.14; F, 11.59%)

Silver Hydroxyfluoberyllate.—This compound can be prepared only after some difficulty. Freshly precipitated silver hydroxide was dissolved in the requisite amount of hydrofluoric acid to afford silver fluoride. Silver hydroxide dissolves in silver fluoride and for that reason the requisite quantity of hydrofluoric acid of known strength should be used. To this solution of silver fluoride equal quantities of beryllium fluoride and beryllium hydroxide (each $\frac{1}{4}$ of the silver salt taken) were added at a low temperature. The resulting solution was digested for about 10 minutes and then it was cooled down to 0° . Excess of alcohol was added to the solution. Too much of alcohol resulted in an immediate precipitation. But as this precipitate was liable to contain other compounds also, addition of alcohol was stopped when the precipitate just began to appear. The solution was kept in a refrigerator. After a few days a colorless solid appeared at the bottom of the solution. This was filtered under suction, washed quickly with 90% alcohol and analysed after drying. (Found: Ag, 71.93; Be, 3.10; F, 19.09. Ag_2BeF_3OH requires Ag, 72.2; Be, 3.02; F, 19.07%). This compound was crystalline under microscope and highly soluble in water.

Hydrazine hydroxyfluoberyllate was prepared by the double decomposition of a solution of thallium hydroxyfluoberyllate with the requisite quantity of hydrazine hydrochloride. After trituration in a mortar the mixture was filtered from the precipitated thallium chloride. The filtrate was concentrated in vacuo over H_2SO_4 . After a few days white crystals of hydrazine hydroxyfluoberyllate appeared. It is highly soluble in water and also fairly soluble in 60% alcohol. (Found: Be, 7.70; F, 49.30. $N_2H_4BF_3OH$ requires Be, 7.60; F, 49.52%).

Tetrammino-cupric Hydroxyfluoberyllate Monohydrate.—To a concentrated solution of copper hydroxyfluoberyllate liquor ammonia was added dropwise with constant stirring. The solution was kept below 13° . Gaseous ammonia was then bubbled through this cooled solution for about half an hour. A slight turbidity appeared due to partial precipitation of beryllium hydroxide. This was filtered quickly and the deep blue filtrate was kept in a quick lime desiccator in an atmosphere of ammonia. Dark blue crystals which appeared after a few days were filtered, washed with ammonia, pressed in the folds of a filter paper and finally dried in an ammonia desiccator over lime. (Found: Be, 3.59; Cu, 27.39; F, 24.08; NH_3 , 28.93. $[Cu_4NH_3] \cdot BeF_3OH, H_2O$ requires Be, 3.88; Cu, 27.32; F, 24.50; NH_3 , 29.27%).

Tetrammino-zinc Hydroxyfluoberyllate.—Freshly precipitated zinc hydroxide was heated with the equimolecular quantity of ammonium hydroxyfluoberyllate and excess of

ammonia. The mixture was kept in a desiccator over quick lime. In two or three days nearly the whole of the solid present dissolved and after a few days, when the solution became sufficiently concentrated, it was filtered. The filtrate was cooled in ice and salt and a slow current of gaseous ammonia was passed through it. After a while finely divided white needle-shaped crystals were obtained. These were filtered, washed with alcohol and then with ether, both saturated with gaseous ammonia, and dried over quick lime in a desiccator in an atmosphere of ammonia. (Found: Be, 3.81; Zn, 29.78; F, 26.01; NH₃, 31.02. [Zn.4NH₃]BeF₃OH requires Be, 4.17; Zn, 30.19; F, 26.32; NH₃, 31.47%).

Tetrammino-cadmium hydroxyfluoberyllate was prepared by the method as described above. (Found: Cd, 42.03; F, 21.18; NH₃, 25.72. [Cd.4NH₃] BeF₃OH requires Cd, 42.63; F, 21.62; NH₃, 25.86%).

Hexammino-nickel hydroxyfluoberyllate was prepared by a similar method described under tetrammino-cupric hydroxyfluoberyllate monohydrate. (Found: Ni, 23.78; F, 23.08; NH₃, 41.72. [Ni(NH₃)₆] BeF₃OH requires Ni, 24.06; F, 23.37; NH₃, 41.90%).

Hexammino-nickel Hydroxyfluoberyllate Potassium Iodide.—When to a concentrated solution of [Ni.6NH₃] BeF₃OH a saturated solution of potassium iodide in aqueous ammonia was added, a sparingly soluble, violet, microcrystalline powder separated. It was dried by the method described above. (Found: F, 9.62; I, 43.78; Ni, 9.92; NH₃, 17.83. [Ni6.NH₃] BeF₃OH. 2KI requires F, 9.90; I, 44.07; Ni, 10.19; NH₃, 17.74%).

The ammino complexes of the hydroxyfluoberyllate group are stable in an atmosphere of ammonia. Evidences for the existence of other ammino compounds of different hydroxyfluoberyllates have also been obtained.

The author acknowledges with pleasure his indebtedness to Prof. P. B. Sarkar, Dr. es. Sc., F.N.I. of Science College, Calcutta, to Prof. N. N. Ray, D.Sc., and Prof. P. C. Raksbit, Ph.D., both of Presidency College, Calcutta; and to Prof. P. Rây, M.A., F. N. I., formerly Prof. of Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science for their kind interest in the work, and also for offering all laboratory facilities.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA.

Received August 21, 1956.